

LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE AS TOOLS FOR NATIONAL UNITY AND INTEGRATION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Nigeria, in recent years, is bedeviled by various crises which are threatening the corporate existence of the country. Among these include the inter-tribal crisis across many Northern States of Nigeria and pockets of occurrence of the clashes between the Fulani and the locals in some Southern States. There are also religious crises and intra-state boundary disputes. We also have political conflict of various kinds, as well as complaints of marginalisation by South-Eastern political leaders and indigenous people of Biafra (IPOB) who seeks the separation of the South-East from Nigeria. There is also the issue of Boko Haram insurgents which is being tackled by government with force. These crises have taken their tolls on Nigeria's nation-building process, they have affected the unity of the country. This paper discusses how national outlook could be cultivated in a multi-ethnic nation like Nigeria. The paper advocates that literary artists can use their works to project the themes of national cohesion and futility of choice of aggression to settle scores. It also advocates the use of appropriate language to communicate our thoughts across ethnic divisions to promote unity and integration.

Keywords: Crises, insurgents, nation-building, unity and integration.

Introduction

The amalgamation of the Northern and Southern Protectorates by Lord Fredrick Lugard in 1914 led to the formation of the country called Nigeria. The British held sway for 46 years until 1960 when Nigeria attained independence and began self-rule. Since independence, some 65 years ago, the country is yet to get it right; yet to cultivate a national outlook. In fact, the country had had to fight a civil war for three years between 1967 – 1970 during which period thousands lost their lives. Even as the country tries to march on after the war, there are recurrent frictions and tensions among the ethnic nationalities. We have religious crisis, Fulani herdsmen and Farmers' crises across many northern States like Taraba, Nassarawa, Adamawa, Plateau, Benue and Kaduna. There is also the intractable Boko Haram insurgency which has consumed thousands of lives, though, the government has recorded some degree of successes checkmating the insurgents. The war is not

over yet because they resort to guerilla tactics. We also have security challenge in Zamfara State occasioned by the activities of the cattle rustlers who rob and kill innocent cattle rearers, farmers and travelers. We have mistrusts among various ethnic groups, there are complaints of domination and marginalisation. Kidnappings, are rampant. All these portend a nation that is speedily drifting towards precipice. Confronted with the various challenges, the Nigerian citizens have not been encouraged to develop positive attitude towards nation-building. However, some of the major challenges threatening the existence of Nigeria are bound to rear their ugly heads even if the country breaks into smaller nations. For example, the Yoruba people of the South-West Nigeria who had been identified by linguists as one of the most linguistically and culturally homogenous people in Nigeria and formally acknowledged as the most religiously tolerant ethnic nationality in Nigeria, as religious crisis seldom occurred among them. But sadly, this narrative has changed in recent times.

Today, in spite of the advantage of its linguistic and cultural homogeneity, the Yorubas also have started playing politics with religion. Sentiments in religion are now being whipped up among them from time to time thereby leading to crisis and hatred for one another by the practitioners of the three religions often engage in fighting which more often than not result in the bloodshed and maiming. An example is the Osun State government policy on school merger and same uniform which was vociferously kicked against by the Christian Association (CAN) who in turn encouraged the Christian pupils to also go to school in choir garments to oppose the use of Hijab by the Muslims pupils in the schools originally founded by Christians. The government's response to that action was that these schools had since been taken over (by the government). The opposition to Hijab wearing in public schools had been a subject of litigation in Lagos State as some Christian groups had approached the court to seek ban on the use of Hijab in Lagos public schools. Also, before the assumption of office by Akinwumi Ambode as the Governor of Lagos State, there had been agitations by many Christian groups who used the media (print and social) and street demonstrations to press for a Christian governor for Lagos State after the expiration of the tenure of Mr. Babatunde Raji Fashola (a Muslim).

In similar fashion, some Muslim organisations had, before the conduct of the last Ekiti State gubernatorial elections, demanded for a Christian/Muslim ticket by the two major political parties. The organisation threatened to ask the Muslim in the state not to vote for the party that did not comply with the demand. The Yoruba socio-cultural and political organisation (Afenifere) had also come under heavy criticism by Yoruba Muslims. The organisation has been tagged a Christian organisation for not having any prominent Muslim among them. Some of these issues, especially the issue of Hijab wearing has become volatile such that it is now a subject of public discourse in the print, and electronic media. In Yoruba land, there is nowadays, a growing acrimony, mistrust and suspicion among adherents of the religions. Some divisive issues in Yoruba land in the South-West as highlighted earlier are ostensibly brought to fore in a bid to counter the argument that the solution to Nigeria's myriad of problems lies in the balkanization of the country into smaller nations. In other words, if the Yoruba people that are acknowledged as one of the most linguistically homogeneous and religiously tolerant ethnic group in the country could in recent years, be embroiled in religious crisis, then the dissolution of Nigeria into federating units is surely not the solution to the challenges confronting the nation. Again, as human beings, we should be concerned about the lots of hundreds of other minority ethnic groups, should the country split. Today, the minority ethnic groups are being protected against total annihilation as people rise to

speak for them and condemn all acts of oppression and injustices perpetuated against them. It is to the benefit of all that efforts are geared towards preserving and promoting Nigeria's unity and integration.

The focus of this paper is on how unity and integration can be fostered in a multilingual and multicultural country such as Nigeria. There have been various studies on how these can be achieved as different governments, civilian or military, since independence have geared efforts towards building Nigeria as a nation., though there is still a long way to go to attain this.

Relevance of Language to Nation Building and Integration

Before we can dwell on language as a phenomenon, there is the need to clarify what a nation (that embodies language) is. Smith (1991) describes the nation as 'a named human community occupying a homeland and having common myths and historical memories, a single public culture, a single economy and common rights and duties for all members' (14). He also identifies a nation as a named community possessing an historic territory, shared myths and memories, a common public culture and common laws and customs (2001:13). In a similar manner, Anderson, (1983:6) views a nation as 'an imagined political community and imagined as both inherently limited and sovereign'. In his own definition, Guibernau (1996:47-48) sees a nation as 'a human group conscious of forming a community, sharing a common culture, attached to a clearly demarcated territory, having a common past and a common project for the future and claiming the right to rule itself'.

From some of these definitions, we deduce that language, race/ethnicity, geography and so on form the basis of a nation. These considerations, to Ernest Renan (1912) offer no sufficient basis in the constitution of modern nations. He cited examples of countries like England and United States, the Latin America and Spain, that speak the same language but do not constitute a single nation. In contrast, Switzerland, which was created by consent of its different parts, contains three or four languages. The most important thing is the desire of Switzerland to unite despite its linguistic variety. However, one thing that has not been controverted by Renan is the indispensability of language whether one or more in any human society. There is no doubt that language has a good number of roles to play in the unity of any nation in the world.

Various scholars have expressed their views on the roles and importance of language in human society. For instance, Olugbuyi and Olaleye (2005:1) state that languages facilitate effective communications which, in turn, guarantee lasting peace and unity. Aina (2006) defines language as a tool for social mobilisation since it is the medium by which people could be educated on issues of unjust traditional practices, the problem and effect of corruption, electioneering, the promotion and consolidation of democracy, combating poverty, understanding constitutional right, dangers of ethnic/religious uprising, etc. Egbokhare (2014) in his own contribution, describes language as permeating all aspects of human endeavour, it exists in a socio-political, cultural and temporal milieu. The fortune of the language is closely tied to the fortune of the people who speak it. Olaoye (2013) posits that language is an indispensable cultural legacy with which all forms of human interactions are carried out. It is capable of destroying or mending relationships. Ogunsiji (2018) asserts that language is a very vital tool in every human society. He imagines how the human society will look like if there is no language at all and he asserts that since languages develop as

the users also develop, it is logical to also say that if the language of a society is not developing, such a society can also not develop.

Yet, another definition that points to language as a human property/attribute used for communication is that given by Crystal (2011) where he notes that: ‘we use language to communicate our ideas and opinions to each other. We use it to ask other people for information and to tell lies. But in all cases, the basic aim is clear. We want the ideas in our head to get into someone else’s head. And for that to happen, we must speak them, write them or sign them’. From the above definitions given by scholars, it can be seen that the significance and contributions of language towards various human activities cannot be over-emphasised. It is seen as a very important ingredient in the development of human societies. It is crucial for the socio-cultural and economic growth of any nation.

However, in spite of the tremendous contributions language can make to the cultural and economic growth as well as unity of nation, unfortunately, Nigeria is a nation with numerous languages. Bamgbose (1971) identifies over 400 languages in the country. Of this number, three of the indigenous languages are referred to as major indigenous languages because of the number of their speakers. The major indigenous languages are Hausa, Yoruba and Igbo. As pointed out by Ogunsiyi (2018) the multiplicity of indigenous languages in the country has made the adoption of any of them as a national language a problem. Udofot (2010) and Adegoke (2011) have identified fear of domination, marginalisation, emotional feeling for ethnic identity and so on as the bane for the adoption of any of the languages as national language. Hence, English as a second language bequeathed by the colonialists now came in to serve as an arbiter for all the indigenous languages.

It has been claimed earlier in this paper that language plays crucial role in every society especially in unifying and integrating the people, the pertinent question therefore is: How can the desired unity and integration be achieved in the Nigerian society that is multilingual and multicultural? The adoption of English in Nigeria as national language may be preferable because it is neutral. However, competence in its use may be greatly impeded if the Nigerian child is not well-grounded in the native language. Similar view had since been expressed by Fletcher and German (1986). They claim good skills in one’s language are essential for future learning as a native language is thought to be a base of thinking. Incomplete first language skills often make learning other languages difficult. Therefore, the indigenous languages are very crucial for the language development the Nigerian child learns from his mother. It is natural to the child who is exposed to it right from the cradle. At last, it serves as a source of his future intellectual, mental and cultural growth. This accounts for why the National Education Policy on Education (NPE 2004) rightly provides that:

- (a) Government shall ensure that the medium of instruction in the pre-primary education is principally the mother-tongue or language of immediate community and to this end will develop the orthography of many more Nigerian languages and produce textbooks in Nigerian languages.
- (b) At the primary school level, government will see to it that the medium of instruction in primary school is initially the mother-tongue or language of the immediate community for the first three years, during this period, English shall be taught as a subject.

Also, Ogunsiyi (2012) asserts that if a child is competent in his or her first language, it will help in improving the mental faculty of such a child even in other subjects. The child first language will help his or her thinking process. He adds that one thinks in his language first before it is brought out in the way one wants it. From the foregoing, one can say that the children who are versed in the first language in a multilingual society such as Nigeria before learning English often generally possess very solid expressive ability and do not have to resort to aggression, abuses, wrong choice of words to express their minds. In summary, therefore, good footing in local languages is crucial to the integration in Nigeria as the child's competence in it enhances his proficiency in English and ultimately national integration.

The Role of English in a Heterogeneous Society like Nigeria

Nigeria is a complex nation with over four hundred languages which make it difficult to adopt one as a national language. English is today seen as a neutral language capable of unifying Nigerians and a tool for national integration. According to Dudley (1973) nation building is the knitting together of threads that hold potential entity together for a sense purpose. These include building a political entity that corresponds to a given territory, based on a generally accepted rules, norms and principles. It also involves the building of institutions which symbolises the political entity of a nation, among which are the bureaucracy, the economy, the civil service, and the judiciary. National integration is the awareness of a common identity amongst the citizens of a country. It means that though we belong to different religion, regions and speak different languages, we recognise the fact that we are all one. This kind of integration is very important in the building of strong and prosperous nation (www.preservearticles.com)

The heterogeneity of Nigeria has helped in the implantation of English in Nigeria. It has however become the unifying language used for communication and interaction among the numerous ethnic nationalities in the country. It is the language of governance, commerce instruction in Nigeria's schools and language of the media. Brosnaham (1963) sums up the role English in Nigeria thus: English is the language of commerce and law, of politics and of administration, of education and of culture, at all levels above to local. An adequate knowledge of English is an indispensable requirement for anyone to rise above or live in any wider context than the village.

Despite the roles English has been playing in unifying and integrating the various ethnic nationalities together to function as one, it is observed that the desired unity, integration, peaceful co-existence, true federalism, development and so on, have not been fully attained. Rather, there is still mutual mistrust, religious crises, disillusionment, anger, etc. across the Nigeria nation.

Today, the Nigerian media, that is the electronic media, the print and social media are very often awash with hate speeches, fake news and divisive commentaries. These actions militate against the unity and integration of the Nigerian people. Also, lack of adequate knowledge of English by the majority of Nigerians or deliberate mischief by some of them contributes to the pervading misunderstanding or misinterpretation of government actions. It is therefore important that government continues to give full backing to every effort that will ensure that every Nigerian is able to use English correctly and appropriately without any ambiguity more so as English serves as a mediator between the people of different ethnic nationalities in

Nigeria. In order to achieve this, the Nigerian child language development foundations must be laid first on the Mother Tongue (MT) or first language.

Literature as an agent of cohesion and integration

Just as language serves as a tool for nation building, unity and integration in Nigeria, literature or other creative works can also be utilized for the same purpose. Literature has been defined variously by several scholars. According to Fatokun (1992) literature suggests a wide range of values and attitudes. To understand an ethnic group and their culture, one may have to turn to their oral and written narratives, their drama and poetry. He adds that a good piece of literature can be regarded as an authentic mirror image of its society and time. Literary artists use language to ridicule or condemn anti-social behaviours such as corruption, assassination, political thuggery, religious intolerance, oppressive rule or dictatorship, any form of human degradation and undemocratic practices.

In utilising literature as a tool for unity and integration, Nigeria literary writers must be concerned with contemporary issues such as politics, socio-cultural and economic realities and make them their recurring thematic preoccupations in order to generate greater awareness and stimuli for change. In other words, the Nigerian creative writers are expected to reflect and refract the realities of the Nigerian society in their works of arts. So, the literary artists' burden is in trying to influence their audience and society positively like insisting that nation building and national unity and integration is achievable.

Among the literary works that dwell on the consequences of war and armed conflict are *The Great Ponds and The Slave* by Elechi Amadi. These novels project the futility of the choice of armed combat to resolve dispute. The narrative reveals that the two warring communities suffered loss of human lives, deprivations and afflictions. The consequence of the choice of war over peaceful resolution can be seen in the regret of Eze Diali in the extract below:

For generations the Ponds have been the cause of wars fought a bitter battle over the Ponds of Wagaba. My father was killed in it. My senior brother was taken prisoner and sold to the Rikwos across the rivers and we never heard of him again. (TGP p.23).

The arrest of the men of Aliakoro and the demand for ransom for their release precipitate the ensuing battles and the spate of attacks and raids the two warring villages carried out against each other. This situation renders the farm unsafe for the people of the villages. The effect of this is seen in the second sentence in the excerpt below:

Some women who prided themselves on their great skill in soup preparation stared at dismay at what now passed for soup. (1) How could soup be prepared without egusi, okro and those wonderful, mushroom?(2) (TGP, p. 76)

Another work by Elechi Amadi that also dwells on unending hostility in the *The Slave*. The narrative reveals the danger of allowing feud to fester as the offspring of the disputing families of Echela and Okani are poised to continue their age-long hostility even when they cannot tell the cause of the dispute.

Also, the works of Elechi Amadi the slave and Ken Saro-Wiwa *Sozaboy* dwell extensively on the futility of disputation and war as the only means of settling dispute. This is exemplified in the extract below:

1. Everyone had noticed Aso's absence at the funeral.
(2) Ovunda a man of few words and soft spoken, could not help confronting Aso, when he met him.
3. 'Why did you not attend Nyege's funeral?'
4. 'Why should I attend a witch's funeral?'
5. 'She hated the very ground I trod on and I hated her's in return.'
6. 'I do not pretend. (7) Attend her funeral? (8) Prrrr!'
9. 'Nobody is saying that Nyege was all good...'
10. 'She was no good at all, admit it.'
11. 'Nyege had her bad points but all hatred ceases at death.'
12. 'Ovunda, you are bothering me (13) The quarrel between Okani and Echela is not of my making, I grew up and met it.'
14. Echela members are unyielding, so we shall see it to the end.'

T. S., p. 88.

Though, Aso, admits that the dispute between the two families began long ago even before his birth, the off springs of the two families are poised to fight it to the end. Through these Free Direct Speech Lines, the fueding families are shown to have engaged in a baseless, unnecessary, senseless and stupid feud which they inherited from their forebears.

The horrendous effect of war is seen in the text *Sozaboy* by Ken Saro Wiwa in the following excerpt.

All our camp don broke down well well. Everywhere was full of pit and pit. And inside one pit, the leg of soza. Everywhere, so so human flesh in small small pieces! Finger, nail, hair, prick, blockus. I just begin cry like woman. Oh foolish man who send me make I go join soza?
(*Sozaboy*, p. 111).

The effects of the needless war is further painted in a clear language. These include annihilation, hunger, diseases, particularly children suffering from kwashiorkor resulting from malnutrition., desolation and loss of lives and property, which manifested towards the tail end to the war. Consequently, both the fighting soldiers and civilians alike in the Biafran side, began to display and express their regret of even starting the war at all, and the devastating

effects of it. This regret is further expressed in the observation and vivid description of the aftermath of the war through Mene:

True true these men were not looking like the people I have known before. If you see how all their eyes have gone inside their head, and all their hair have become palm oil colour and they have dirty dirty rag shirt and all bones are shaking inside their body, I am telling you, if you see all these things, and you think about them very well, you will know at once, that war is a very bad and stupid game (p. 151).

From the extracts isolated above, we observe that literature too is capable of engendering unity and integration among the various ethnic groups in Nigeria society. The narrative proposes the use of dialogue to resolve dispute instead of confrontation, the outcome of which is distasteful. In this way, literary works can be used to reduce greatly the recurring hostilities between communities, ethnic nationalities or groups thereby promoting national unity and integration. So, instead of confrontation or other violent options, literary artists should endeavour to include in their creative works the need to adopt peaceful means of settling disputes through dialogue. Such creative works should cover the three genre of literature: poetry, drama and prose; and other outlets like films, television drama, series and online comedy sketches.

Conclusion

The study highlights the importance of language as a characteristic that is peculiar to human society and thus, it is doubtful if there can be any human society without language. Therefore, having a language that can be referred to as a national one in country like Nigeria is highly desirable.

The study notes that Nigeria is an amalgam of numerous ethnic nationalities, languages and culture. Since independence, successive governments have geared efforts towards nation building but the much desired unity and integration have not been achieved. It highlights many socio-economic and political challenges that have been bedeviling the nation over the years and now which have been threatening the continued existence of Nigeria as a nation.

Therefore, the study proposes language and literature as tools for achieving national outlook. Recognising that Nigeria is a multilingual nation, it advocates that English which is preferable to all Nigerian people should still be adopted as the national language and thoroughly taught to our children in schools and colleges. This is because it is the instrument that can be used by all for national unity and integration.

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